

Ongoing Development of Non-reflective Boundary Conditions for Euler and Navier-Stokes Equations via the Discontinuous Galerkin Framework

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In an effort to implement non-reflective boundary conditions (NRBCs) in the context of the high-order discontinuous Galerkin (dG) finite element method (FEM), the perfectly matched layer (PML) and the Navier-Stokes characteristic boundary condition (NSCBC) are considered for the compressible Navier-Stokes and Euler equations. A conservative-formulation Cartesian-based two-dimensional nodal dG solver and an entropy-formulation curvilinear-based three-dimensional modal dG solver are used. For the first, a low-storage fourth-order Runge-Kutta (LSRK4) is employed for time marching, while for the second, a strong-stability-preserving third-order Runge-Kutta (SSPRK3) is selected. Results include classical problems such as the isentropic vortex and the Kelvin-Helmholtz instability for the nodal solver, while a spherical pressure disturbance and a flow past a hump are considered for the modal solver. Both PML and NSCBC prove very promising in the context of the dG method. Future work will entail the development and testing of the PML in their viscous-term inclusion, as well as the compatibility conditions on edges and corners for the NSCBC on more rigorous test cases.

I. Nomenclature

ρ	=	density
p	=	pressure
u	=	velocity in the x -direction
v	=	velocity in the y -direction
w	=	velocity in the z -direction
E	=	energy
T	=	temperature
γ	=	specific heat ratio
M	=	Mach number
a	=	speed of sound
R	=	gas constant
C_p	=	coefficient of pressure
μ	=	dynamic viscosity
U_0	=	bulk velocity in x -direction
Λ	=	diagonal eigenvalue matrix
S	=	eigenvector matrix
Q	=	primitive variables
U	=	conservative variables
V	=	entropy variables
W	=	working variables
\mathcal{L}	=	wave amplitudes in the normal-direction
ℓ	=	Lagrange polynomial
ψ	=	Legendre polynomial
N_p	=	number of DOFs in an element

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II. Introduction

IN certain applications, open, farfield, or unbounded boundaries are a common situation, dictated by the physics being described. Such scenarios are not uncommon in computational aeroacoustics (CAA), computational electromagnetics (CEM) and computational fluid dynamics (CFD) communities. These boundaries do not correspond to a physical condition, such as the ones induced by walls, rather they are a mathematical formulation utilized in order to reduce the computational domain in an abstract manner.

Discretely speaking, open boundaries need to be truncated and taken care of numerically by so-called non-reflecting boundary conditions (NRBCs). Many variants of such boundary conditions (BCs) exist, since throughout the last few decades, different forms were devised. Some rely on an asymptotic-based condition [1, 2], others consider a characteristic-based approach [3] while others make use of an additional, non-physical region in order to gradually alter the behavior of the equations [4] or exponentially damp the solution [5]. Currently, the two most commonly used class of methods fall into categories of either characteristic-based or buffer-zone techniques. Hence, only these two are highlighted.

One widely used group of NRBCs is based on characteristic theory. In such a method, the partial differential equation (PDE) describing the flow physics is decomposed into its canonical form and, according to the relevant wave-amplitude, incoming information into the domain is canceled at the specified boundary. Other group of methods, often referred to as buffer-zone techniques make use of an additional layer that extends the domain of interest into a *fictitious* region. There is a range of different techniques that use this approach. Some simply add a damping factor in order to exponentially attenuate the incoming fluctuations, while others increase the flow speed into supersonic regimes and hence eliminate any reflections back. Either way, the idea behind the fictitious extension is to modify the governing equations in such a way to reduce the reflections at the interface with the physical domain. All in all, both groups of NRBC considerations try to best mimic an ‘infinite’ domain, in the discrete sense.

Unsurprisingly, each of these methods has its advantages and shortcomings. As it stands out, nowadays, the usual way of treating a NRBC is by means of a characteristic boundary condition (CBC), especially since this is computationally efficient to implement. However, one of the drawbacks of such a method is that it treats the traveling waves predominantly in a one-dimensional manner. For a one-dimensional problem, this works excellently, but for dimensions higher than one, this mainly suppresses the waves normal to the boundary. Many alterations of such methods exist in order to better account for the transverse/parallel effects. By far, the most renowned variant is the Navier-Stokes characteristic boundary condition (NSCBC) [6]. On the other hand, one of the most promising buffer-zone techniques is that based on the perfectly matched layer (PML).

After introducing the PML technique for suppressing electromagnetic waves in [5], its inclusion to CFD applications started gaining momentum. This endeavor was mainly due to the initial work in [7] for solving the linearized Euler equations in the context of aeroacoustic applications. In fact, the split formulation as proposed in [5, 7], was demonstrated to result in a weakly well-posed mathematical expression, allowing for numerical instabilities, as pointed out in [8, 9]. This was later revised and fixed in [10], after realizing that unlike in CEM, in CAA and CFD, the problem was due to a difference in direction in the group and phase velocities. Currently, the PML method is being actively developed and incorporated in different discretization methods for non-linear as well as viscous problems [11–13].

Another important criteria when simulating wave phenomena over large distances, as usually encountered in CAA problems, is that the information must not be numerically altered. In other words, discretization errors in space and time, both dissipative and dispersive, should be relatively negligible, otherwise the fluctuations will be damped out in time across the grid. To allow the usage of unstructured grids, the discontinuous Galerkin method is employed, as opposed to conventional finite-difference time-domain (FDTD) methods which commonly utilize dispersion-relation-preserving finite difference schemes [2].

The discontinuous Galerkin (dG) method was initially introduced for solving a neutron transport problem [14], a hyperbolic (PDE). Its main advantage is the mix between numerical stability, high-order polynomial approximations, parallelization efficiency and handling complicated geometries. Accordingly, such a method reduces the need for an adaptive stencil near the boundaries, as often encountered in finite difference methods or high-order finite-volume methods. This helps in paving the way for a more robust and efficient simulation. Moreover, discontinuities between the physical and fictitious regions (e.g. PML) are handled efficiently, because of the intrinsic discontinuous nature of the dG method.

In this paper, a nodal-based dG solver [15] for the Euler equations in two-dimensions is considered. Then a modal-based dG solver for the Navier-Stokes equations in three-dimensions is employed. A PML formulation and a CBC approach, based on the NSCBC technique [6, 16], are used in the nodal version. Only a NSCBC approach is implemented in the modal version for now. Tests and comparisons are done on multiple canonical test cases, such

as isentropic vortex, Kelvin-Helmholtz instabilities and pressure disturbances, before trying this framework on more challenging situations, like the flow past a hump.

The content of this paper is structured as follows. In Section III, the governing equations of fluid flow are presented, i.e. the (compressible) Navier-Stokes equations. Then, non-reflective boundary conditions, such as the PML and the NSCBC are introduced in Section IV. The numerical methods are described in Section V, starting from the spatial nodal and modal dG finite element method and then into explicit temporal marching schemes, mainly the fourth-order five-stage low-storage Runge-Kutta (LSRK4) and the third-order strong-stability-preserving Runge-Kutta (SSPRK3). Afterwards, the results are displayed in Section VI, starting from the nodal version, before moving into the modal one. Finally, the conclusion and future work are presented in Section VII.

III. Governing Equations of Fluid Flow

The full Navier-Stokes equations, in their compressible form, describing the physics of fluid flow, in Cartesian coordinates, are given by

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial \mathbf{W}} \frac{\partial \mathbf{W}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}^i}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{G}^i}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{H}^i}{\partial z} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}^v}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{G}^v}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{H}^v}{\partial z}, \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{W} are the working variables, which may be either the conservative variables \mathbf{U} or the entropy variables \mathbf{V} , defined as

$$\mathbf{U} = \begin{pmatrix} \rho \\ \rho u \\ \rho v \\ \rho w \\ \rho E \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{V} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\gamma-s}{\gamma-1} - \frac{\rho}{2p}(u^2 + v^2 + w^2) \\ \frac{\rho u}{p} \\ \frac{\rho v}{p} \\ \frac{\rho w}{p} \\ -\frac{\rho}{p} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

where $s = \ln(p/\rho^\gamma)$ is the entropy and $\partial \mathbf{U} / \partial \mathbf{W}$ is the Jacobian used for conversion in between conservative and entropy variables, if $\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{U}$, it is the identity matrix. The inviscid fluxes are given by

$$\mathbf{F}^i = \begin{pmatrix} \rho u \\ \rho u^2 + p \\ \rho uv \\ \rho uw \\ \rho uH \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{G}^i = \begin{pmatrix} \rho v \\ \rho uv \\ \rho v^2 + p \\ \rho vw \\ \rho vH \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{H}^i = \begin{pmatrix} \rho w \\ \rho uw \\ \rho vw \\ \rho w^2 + p \\ \rho wH \end{pmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

where $H = E + p/\rho$ is the enthalpy, while the viscous fluxes are given by

$$\mathbf{F}^v = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ \tau_{xx} \\ \tau_{xy} \\ \tau_{xz} \\ u\tau_{xx} + v\tau_{xy} + w\tau_{xz} - q_x \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{G}^v = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ \tau_{xy} \\ \tau_{yy} \\ \tau_{yz} \\ u\tau_{xy} + v\tau_{yy} + w\tau_{yz} - q_y \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{H}^v = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ \tau_{xz} \\ \tau_{yz} \\ \tau_{zz} \\ u\tau_{xz} + v\tau_{yz} + w\tau_{zz} - q_z \end{pmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

Here, a Newtonian fluid is assumed for the viscous stress tensor

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{xx} &= 2\mu \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \lambda \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial z} \right), & \tau_{xy} &= \mu \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right), \\ \tau_{yy} &= 2\mu \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + \lambda \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial z} \right), & \tau_{xz} &= \mu \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right), \\ \tau_{zz} &= 2\mu \frac{\partial w}{\partial z} + \lambda \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial z} \right), & \tau_{yz} &= \mu \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \right), \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where μ is the dynamic viscosity, assuming Stoke's hypothesis for the second viscosity $\lambda = -2\mu/3$, and the heat flux is modeled via Fourier's law

$$q_x = -\kappa \frac{\partial T}{\partial x}, \quad q_y = -\kappa \frac{\partial T}{\partial y}, \quad q_z = -\kappa \frac{\partial T}{\partial z}, \quad (6)$$

and the thermal conductivity is given as $\kappa = \mu C_p / \text{Pr}$, where Pr is the Prandtl number, defined as the ratio of the momentum diffusivity to thermal diffusivity.

In the above, ρ is the density, u , v and w are the velocity components, p is the pressure, E the energy and T is the temperature. Moreover, a calorically perfect gas is assumed, hence the below equation of state holds

$$p = \rho RT, \quad (7)$$

where $R = C_p - C_v$ is the gas constant, with C_p and C_v being the specific heats at constant pressure and volume, respectively, $\gamma = C_p / C_v$ is the ratio of specific heats, and the speed of sound is $a = \sqrt{\gamma p / \rho}$.

Note, both inviscid and viscous fluxes, in their quasi-linear form are functions of the working variables. Additionally, the (non-linear) Euler equations are a special case of Equation (1) by ignoring the viscous terms.

IV. Non-reflective Boundary Treatment

A. Perfectly Matched Layer

The first step in deriving a perfectly matched layer is to decompose the flow state into a pseudo-mean component and a fluctuating one as follows: $\mathbf{W} = \overline{\mathbf{W}} + \mathbf{w}'$, where the former satisfies a steady-state as follows

$$\left(\frac{\partial \overline{\mathbf{F}}^i}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \overline{\mathbf{G}}^i}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \overline{\mathbf{H}}^i}{\partial z} \right) - \left(\frac{\partial \overline{\mathbf{F}}^v}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \overline{\mathbf{G}}^v}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \overline{\mathbf{H}}^v}{\partial z} \right) = \mathbf{0}, \quad (8)$$

where $\overline{\mathbf{F}}^i = \mathbf{F}_i^i(\overline{\mathbf{W}})$ and $\overline{\mathbf{F}}^v = \mathbf{F}_i^v(\overline{\mathbf{g}}_{x_i}, \overline{\mathbf{W}})$, with $\overline{\mathbf{g}}_{x_i} = \mathbf{g}_{x_i}(\overline{\mathbf{W}})$. The equations for the perturbed state may be derived by subtracting Equation (8) from Equation (1) to obtain

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{w}'}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\mathbf{F}^i - \overline{\mathbf{F}}^i] + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} [\mathbf{G}^i - \overline{\mathbf{G}}^i] + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} [\mathbf{H}^i - \overline{\mathbf{H}}^i] = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\mathbf{F}^v - \overline{\mathbf{F}}^v] + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} [\mathbf{G}^v - \overline{\mathbf{G}}^v] + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} [\mathbf{H}^v - \overline{\mathbf{H}}^v], \quad (9)$$

and for the working-variable gradients

$$\mathbf{g}'_x = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\mathbf{W} - \overline{\mathbf{W}}], \quad \mathbf{g}'_y = \frac{\partial}{\partial y} [\mathbf{W} - \overline{\mathbf{W}}], \quad \mathbf{g}'_z = \frac{\partial}{\partial z} [\mathbf{W} - \overline{\mathbf{W}}]. \quad (10)$$

Without loss of generality, we assume that the mean-flow direction is in the x -direction. The PML derivation will first address a buffer zone that is extruded in only the x -direction. The remaining y - and z -layers are deduced analogously.

In order to arrive at a stable PML formulation, a three-step method is used [17]. First, a dispersion-relation correction via a transformation is applied, followed by a Fourier transform. To avoid any misalignment in between the phase and group velocities, the following space-time transformations are introduced

$$\tilde{t} \longrightarrow t + \beta x, \quad \tilde{x} \longrightarrow x, \quad \tilde{y} \longrightarrow y - V_0 t, \quad \tilde{z} \longrightarrow z - W_0 t, \quad (11)$$

where V_0 , W_0 are the bulk velocities in the transverse, y - and z -directions, respectively, and the parameter β is dependent on the pseudo-mean flow only. The first transformation corrects the instabilities arising from the acoustics waves [18], while the latter three address instabilities due to entropy/vorticity waves [19], due to the presence of cross-flow. Consequently, the following changes in the partial derivatives occur

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \longrightarrow \frac{\partial}{\partial \tilde{t}} - V_0 \frac{\partial}{\partial \tilde{y}} - W_0 \frac{\partial}{\partial \tilde{z}}, \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \longrightarrow \frac{\partial}{\partial \tilde{x}} + \beta \frac{\partial}{\partial \tilde{t}}, \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \longrightarrow \frac{\partial}{\partial \tilde{y}}, \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \longrightarrow \frac{\partial}{\partial \tilde{z}}. \quad (12)$$

Taking this new transformation and applying it on Equations (9) and (10), one gets

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathbf{w}'}{\partial t} - V_0 \frac{\partial \mathbf{w}'}{\partial y} - W_0 \frac{\partial \mathbf{w}'}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\mathbf{F}^i_-] + \beta \frac{\partial}{\partial t} [\mathbf{F}^i_-] + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} [\mathbf{G}^i_-] + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} [\mathbf{H}^i_-] &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\mathbf{F}^v_-] + \beta \frac{\partial}{\partial t} [\mathbf{F}^v_-] + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} [\mathbf{G}^v_-] + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} [\mathbf{H}^v_-], \\ \mathbf{g}'_x &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\mathbf{W}_-] + \beta \frac{\partial}{\partial t} [\mathbf{W}_-], \quad \mathbf{g}'_y = \frac{\partial}{\partial y} [\mathbf{W}_-], \quad \mathbf{g}'_z = \frac{\partial}{\partial z} [\mathbf{W}_-], \end{aligned}$$

where the notation $[\mathbf{F}_-] = \mathbf{F} - \bar{\mathbf{F}}$ is introduced for conciseness. Utilizing a Fourier transform, one obtains the frequency-domain equivalent of the above expressions

$$\begin{aligned} (-i\tilde{\omega}) \left(\widehat{\mathbf{w}'} + \beta [\widehat{\mathbf{F}^i_-}] - \beta [\widehat{\mathbf{F}^v_-}] \right) - V_0 \frac{\partial \widehat{\mathbf{w}'}}{\partial y} - W_0 \frac{\partial \widehat{\mathbf{w}'}}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\widehat{\mathbf{F}^i_-}] + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} [\widehat{\mathbf{G}^i_-}] + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} [\widehat{\mathbf{H}^i_-}] &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\widehat{\mathbf{F}^v_-}] + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} [\widehat{\mathbf{G}^v_-}] + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} [\widehat{\mathbf{H}^v_-}], \\ \widehat{\mathbf{g}'}_x &= (-i\tilde{\omega}) \beta [\widehat{\mathbf{W}_-}] + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\widehat{\mathbf{W}_-}], \quad \widehat{\mathbf{g}'}_y = \frac{\partial}{\partial y} [\widehat{\mathbf{W}_-}], \quad \widehat{\mathbf{g}'}_z = \frac{\partial}{\partial z} [\widehat{\mathbf{W}_-}], \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where $\tilde{\omega}$ is the angular frequency, and the symbol $(\widehat{\cdot})$ corresponds to the Fourier transformed variable.

The second step is to apply a *complex* change-of-variables on the spatial gradient in the flow-direction (x -direction) as follows

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \rightarrow \frac{1}{1 + i \frac{\sigma_x}{\tilde{\omega}}} \frac{\partial}{\partial x}, \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \rightarrow \frac{\partial}{\partial y}, \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \rightarrow \frac{\partial}{\partial z}, \quad (14)$$

where σ_x is the damping coefficient in the buffer zone in the x -direction. To reduce the number of auxiliary variables needed, a *split* approach is used [7]. The perturbed variable is decomposed as follows

$$\mathbf{w}' = \mathbf{q}_1 + \mathbf{q}_2 + \mathbf{q}_3, \quad (15)$$

where the expressions in Equation (13) are split based on the spatial gradients.

In the third step, substituting Equations (14) and (15) into Equation (13), reverting back to time-domain and in the original variables, one obtains the final x -layer PML version of Equation (1)

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{W}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}^i}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{G}^i}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{H}^i}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}^v}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial \mathbf{G}^v}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial \mathbf{H}^v}{\partial z} + \sigma_x \beta ([\mathbf{F}^i_-] - [\mathbf{F}^v_-]) + \sigma_x \mathbf{q} = \mathbf{0}, \quad (16a)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{q}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\mathbf{F}^i_-] - \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\mathbf{F}^v_-] + V_0 \frac{\partial \mathbf{q}}{\partial y} + W_0 \frac{\partial \mathbf{q}}{\partial z} + \sigma_x \beta ([\mathbf{F}^i_-] - [\mathbf{F}^v_-]) + \sigma_x \mathbf{q} = \mathbf{0}, \quad (16b)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{r}}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\mathbf{W}_-] + V_0 \frac{\partial \mathbf{r}}{\partial y} + W_0 \frac{\partial \mathbf{r}}{\partial z} - \sigma_x \beta [\mathbf{W}_-] + \sigma_x \mathbf{r} = \mathbf{0}, \quad (16c)$$

where \mathbf{q} and \mathbf{r} are auxiliary variables introduced in the inviscid and viscous terms, respectively. Additionally, the resulting working-variable gradients are

$$\mathbf{g}_x = \frac{\partial \mathbf{W}}{\partial x} - \sigma_x \mathbf{r} + \sigma_x \beta [\mathbf{W}_-], \quad \mathbf{g}_y = \frac{\partial \mathbf{W}}{\partial y}, \quad \mathbf{g}_z = \frac{\partial \mathbf{W}}{\partial z}, \quad (17a)$$

which are used to evaluate the viscous fluxes.

Note, in the case of $\sigma_x = 0$, the PML expressions in Equations (16a) to (16c) and (17a) are reduced into the original Navier-Stokes equations given in Equation (1). Moreover, for flows with a constant pseudo-mean density, [12] reported that $\beta \approx U_0 / (a^2 - U_0^2)$ is a good approximation, where U_0 is the bulk velocity in the flow (x -)direction.

B. Navier-Stokes Characteristic Boundary Condition

The first step in constructing a Navier-Stokes characteristic boundary condition is to cast Equation (1) in terms of its characteristic variables. To accomplish this, first a conversion from the working variables to the primitive ones is done in order to obtain the below quasi-linear primitive-based form

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{Q}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{S}_x \Lambda_x \mathbf{S}_x^{-1} \frac{\partial \mathbf{Q}}{\partial x} + \mathbf{S}_y \Lambda_y \mathbf{S}_y^{-1} \frac{\partial \mathbf{Q}}{\partial y} + \mathbf{S}_z \Lambda_z \mathbf{S}_z^{-1} \frac{\partial \mathbf{Q}}{\partial z} = \widetilde{\mathbf{S}}^v, \quad (18)$$

where Λ_i , S_i and S_i^{-1} are the eigenvalue, left and right eigenvector matrices along the i th direction, respectively, with the primitive variables denoted as $\mathbf{Q} = (\rho, u, v, w, p)^T$, and the viscous terms are presented by

$$\widetilde{\mathbf{S}}^v = \frac{\partial \mathbf{Q}}{\partial \mathbf{W}} \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{F}^v}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{G}^v}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{H}^v}{\partial z} \right). \quad (19)$$

Without loss of generality, we consider a boundary normal to the x -direction. The corresponding characteristic form may be achieved by multiplying the relevant normal right eigenvector matrix from the left with Equation (18)

$$\begin{aligned} S_x^{-1} \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{Q}}{\partial t} + \mathcal{D}_x + \widetilde{\mathbf{G}} \frac{\partial \mathbf{Q}}{\partial y} + \widetilde{\mathbf{H}} \frac{\partial \mathbf{Q}}{\partial z} - \widetilde{\mathbf{S}}^v \right) &= \mathbf{0}, \\ \frac{\partial \mathbf{W}}{\partial t} + \mathcal{L} - \mathcal{T} - \mathbf{S}^v &= \mathbf{0}, \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

where for convenience $\widetilde{\mathbf{G}} = S_y \Lambda_y S_y^{-1}$ and $\widetilde{\mathbf{H}} = S_z \Lambda_z S_z^{-1}$ are the eigendecomposed inviscid y - and z -fluxes, respectively, $\mathbf{W} = S_x^{-1} \mathbf{Q}$ are the characteristic variables in the normal (x -)direction, $\mathcal{D} = S_x \mathcal{L}$ is the x -dimensional local one-dimensional inviscid (LODI) system [6], the viscous terms are $\mathbf{S}^v = S_x^{-1} \widetilde{\mathbf{S}}^v$, while the vector containing the wave amplitudes and the transverse gradients are each given, respectively, by

$$\mathcal{L} = \Lambda_x S_x^{-1} \frac{\partial \mathbf{Q}}{\partial x}, \quad \mathcal{T} = -S_x^{-1} \left(\widetilde{\mathbf{G}} \frac{\partial \mathbf{Q}}{\partial y} + \widetilde{\mathbf{H}} \frac{\partial \mathbf{Q}}{\partial z} \right). \quad (21)$$

Note, when the transverse and diffusion terms are neglected in Equation (20), it reduces to the so-called LODI relations. In case the transverse terms are retained, additional compatibility conditions between different boundary conditions at edges and corners need to be taken into account [16].

The rationale behind a characteristic boundary treatment is, after decomposing the PDE into its characteristic form, depending on the sign of the relevant normal eigenvalues, one is able to distinguish between incoming (unknown) and outgoing (known) information with respect to the domain. These five eigenvalues correspond to two acoustic waves, two vorticity waves and an entropy wave.

In the case of a subsonic inlet boundary stationed normal to the x -direction, there exists four incoming waves (an acoustic, two vorticity and an entropy) and one outgoing wave (acoustic). To impose a partially non-reflecting inlet boundary based on the temperature and velocity, the following are prescribed

$$\mathcal{L}_\phi = \eta_\phi \frac{a(1 - \overline{M}^2)}{2l_x} (u - u_\infty) + \mathcal{T}_\phi + \mathbf{S}_\phi^v, \quad (22a)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_2 = -\eta_2 \frac{\rho R}{a l_x} (T - T_\infty) + \mathcal{T}_2 + \mathbf{S}_2^v, \quad (22b)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_3 = \eta_3 \frac{a}{l_x} (v - v_\infty) + \mathcal{T}_3 + \mathbf{S}_3^v, \quad (22c)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_4 = \eta_4 \frac{a}{l_x} (w - w_\infty) + \mathcal{T}_4 + \mathbf{S}_4^v, \quad (22d)$$

where η are relaxation coefficients, l_x is a characteristic length and \overline{M} is the Mach number taken as the average over the entire boundary, and the acoustic wave index depends on the boundary placement: $\phi = 1$ if the boundary is towards the end of domain, otherwise $\phi = 5$. All $(\cdot)_\infty$ subscripts denote a target or reference state. If this is not used, a drift in the mean-target state will occur, hence the need for a *partially* non-reflecting approach [6].

In the case of a subsonic outlet boundary stationed normal to the x -direction, there exists one incoming wave (acoustic) and four outgoing waves (an acoustic, two vorticity and an entropy). To impose a partially non-reflecting outlet boundary based on the pressure, the following is enforced

$$\mathcal{L}_\phi = \sigma \frac{1 - \overline{M}^2}{2\rho l_x} (p - p_\infty) - (1 - \beta_l) \mathcal{L}'_\phi + (1 - \beta_t) \overline{\mathcal{T}}_\phi + \mathbf{S}_\phi^v, \quad (23)$$

where σ is a relaxation coefficient, $\mathcal{T} = \overline{\mathcal{T}} - \mathcal{L}'$ is decomposed into an uncoupled term $\overline{\mathcal{T}}$ and a coupled term \mathcal{L}' , based on the material derivative taken with respect to the bicharacteristics at the boundary [20]. According to their work,

$\beta_l = 1$ is selected in order to cancel any coupling between incoming and outgoing waves, while β_r is a constant that controls the remaining transverse term contribution.

In the context of the dG method used, NSCBCs are applied on the external/ghost state via a polynomial-correction approach (PC-NSCBC). In mathematical terms, for the considered boundary location, this looks like

$$\mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{x}_\partial) = \frac{\mathcal{G}_x - \sum_{i=1, i \neq \partial}^{N_p} \mathbf{Q}_i \partial_x \ell_i(\mathbf{x}_\partial)}{\partial_x \ell_\partial(\mathbf{x}_\partial)}, \quad (24)$$

where the subscript $(\cdot)_\partial$ implies the index corresponding to the node at the boundary of each element and \mathcal{G}_x is the spatial derivative of the primitive variables based on the wave amplitude definition and is expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{G}_x &= \partial_x \mathbf{Q}, \\ &= \mathbf{S}_x \mathbf{\Lambda}_x \mathcal{L}, \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

whereby the specified characteristic boundary is applied via the \mathcal{L} vector. Remaining terms are defined in Section V.A.

V. Numerical Method

A. Discontinuous Galerkin Method

The discontinuous Galerkin finite element formulation is illustrated below. Consider a triangulation Ω of non-overlapping elements D : $\Omega = \bigcup_k D^{(k)}$, where k denotes the elements with global solution \mathbf{W}

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{W}(\mathbf{x}, t) &\approx \mathbf{W}_h(\mathbf{x}, t), \\ &= \bigoplus_k \mathbf{W}_h^{(k)}(\mathbf{x}^{(k)}, t), \quad \mathbf{x}^{(k)} \in D^{(k)}, \end{aligned}$$

where the subscript $(\cdot)_h$ denotes an approximated quantity and on each element, Legendre-Gauss-Lobatto (LGL) points are used for the location of the degrees-of-freedom (DOFs) in order to avoid the infamous Runge phenomenon [15, chap. 3]. Note, the subscript h will be dismissed from now on, out of convenience.

Similar to a continuous finite element method, the weak formulation is sought. This is done by multiplying the PDE, now comprised of *trial* functions, with a *test* function and integrating over each element. In line with a Galerkin formulation, the test and trial functions are selected to be of the same basis functions. In a generic formulation, the working variables, be it via a *modal* or a *nodal* variant of the dG scheme are assumed to vary, respectively, according to

$$\mathbf{W}^{(k)}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \sum_{j=1}^{N_p} \widehat{\mathbf{W}}_j^{(k)} \psi_j(\mathbf{x}^{(k)}), \quad (26a)$$

$$= \sum_{j=1}^{N_p} \mathbf{W}_j^{(k)} \ell_j(\mathbf{x}^{(k)}), \quad (26b)$$

where $\widehat{\mathbf{W}}$ are the modal expansion coefficients, $N_p^{(k)} = N^{(k)} + 1$ is the number of DOFs (degrees-of-freedom) in element $D^{(k)}$, while $N^{(k)}$ is the polynomial order that describes it. In this work, we restrict ourselves to tensor-product elements, therefore $\psi(\mathbf{x}) = \psi(x)\psi(y)\psi(z)$ is a tensor-product of one-dimensional (orthonormal) Legendre polynomial basis, and $\ell(\mathbf{x}) = \ell(x)\ell(y)\ell(z)$ denotes the tensor-product of one-dimensional Lagrange polynomials, defined as

$$\ell_m(x) = \prod_{\substack{n=1 \\ n \neq m}}^{N_p} \frac{x - r_n}{r_m - r_n}, \quad (27)$$

with the property $\ell_m(r_n) = \delta_{mn}$ with δ denoting the Kronecker delta. A concise way to convert in between the two forms is via

$$\mathcal{V} \widehat{\mathbf{W}} = \mathbf{W}, \quad (28)$$

where $\mathcal{V}_{ij} = \psi_{j-1}(r_i)$ is the Vandermonde matrix, with \mathbf{r} being the DOFs.

As an illustration, taking Equation (1) in its one-dimensional form, the resulting weak formulation, based on a modal approach, reads

$$\partial_t \int_{D^{(k)}} \psi_m \mathbf{J} \mathbf{W} dx + [\mathbf{Vol}]^i - [\mathbf{Surf}]^i + [\mathbf{Vol}]^v - [\mathbf{Surf}]^v - \theta [\mathbf{Sym}]^v + [\mathbf{Pen}]^v = \mathbf{0}, \quad (m = 1, \dots, N_p), \quad (29)$$

where θ being a constant used in the selection of the interior penalty method and $\mathbf{J} = \partial \mathbf{U} / \partial \mathbf{W}$ is the Jacobian. The inviscid part is given as

$$[\mathbf{Vol}]^i = \int_{D^{(k)}} \partial_x \psi_m \mathbf{F}^i dx, \quad (30a)$$

$$[\mathbf{Surf}]^i = \int_{\Gamma}^{(k)} \psi_m \mathbf{F}_*^i n_x ds, \quad (30b)$$

where n_x denotes the normal in the x -direction on the boundary $\Gamma^{(k)} = \partial D^{(k)}$, while the asterisk subscript/superscript implies an artificial dissipation term based on a Riemann solver [21]. The viscous part is given by a symmetric interior penalty method (SIPM) [22–24] as follows

$$[\mathbf{Vol}]^v = \int_{D^{(k)}} \partial_x \psi_m \left(\mathbf{K}_{11}^W \partial_x \mathbf{W} + \mathbf{K}_{12}^W \partial_y \mathbf{W} + \mathbf{K}_{13}^W \partial_z \mathbf{W} \right) dx, \quad (31a)$$

$$[\mathbf{Surf}]^v = \int_{\Gamma^{(k)}} \psi_m \left\{ \left[\mathbf{K}_{11}^W \partial_x \mathbf{W} + \mathbf{K}_{12}^W \partial_y \mathbf{W} + \mathbf{K}_{13}^W \partial_z \mathbf{W} \right] \right\} n_x ds \quad (31b)$$

$$[\mathbf{Sym}]^v = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Gamma^{(k)}} \left(\partial_x \psi_m \left[\mathbf{K}_{11}^W \mathbf{W} \right] + \partial_y \psi_m \left[\mathbf{K}_{21}^W \mathbf{W} \right] + \partial_z \psi_m \left[\mathbf{K}_{31}^W \mathbf{W} \right] \right) n_x ds, \quad (31c)$$

$$[\mathbf{Pen}]^v = \sigma_h^{(k)} \int_{\Gamma^{(k)}} \psi_m \mathbf{J}^* \llbracket \mathbf{W} \rrbracket ds, \quad (31d)$$

where \mathbf{J}^* is the averaged Jacobian in between the two neighboring elements sharing the same face, σ_h is a penalty coefficient, $\llbracket w \rrbracket = (w^- + w^+)/2$ is the average operator and $\llbracket w \rrbracket = w^- - w^+$ denotes a jump operator, where the minus and plus superscripts correspond to the internal and external (neighboring) element, respectively. The viscous fluxes, in their quasi-linear state are given by the below x -diffusion matrices

$$\mathbf{F}^v = \mathbf{K}_{11}^W \frac{\partial \mathbf{W}}{\partial x} + \mathbf{K}_{12}^W \frac{\partial \mathbf{W}}{\partial y} + \mathbf{K}_{13}^W \frac{\partial \mathbf{W}}{\partial z}, \quad (32)$$

where, in the case the working variables are entropy-based, then the diffusion matrices are symmetric $\mathbf{K}_{ij}^V = \mathbf{K}_{ji}^V$. Moreover, when computing the integrals, over-integration was used with thrice the polynomial degree per dimension, in order to reduce aliasing errors.

B. Temporal Discretization

1. Low-storage Runge-Kutta

A convenient variant of the explicit Runge-Kutta (RK) scheme used in this work is the fourth-order five-stage low-storage Runge-Kutta given in [25]. This low-storage RK is of 4th-order accuracy in time for both linear and non-linear problems. The only caveat in using this scheme is that 5, instead of 4, stages are used, although only 2 additional memory storage of the solution is required. A justification to the extra stage of evaluation is the ability to use larger time steps than an otherwise classic RK4 can handle [15]; besides, the reduction in memory storage is highly pragmatic, given how demanding a dG scheme can be. The LSRK4 scheme is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{k}_i &= a_i \mathbf{k}_{i-1} + \delta t \cdot \mathbf{Res} \left(t^n + c_i \delta t, \mathbf{p}_{i-1} \right), \\ \mathbf{p}_i &= \mathbf{p}_{i-1} + b_i \mathbf{k}_i, \\ \mathbf{W}^{n+1} &= \mathbf{p}_5, \end{aligned} \quad (i = 1, \dots, 5), \quad (33)$$

with the n -superscripts denoting the current time, δt being the time step, \mathbf{Res} the spatial residual operator, \mathbf{p}_i is a tentative solution with $\mathbf{p}_0 = \mathbf{W}^n$ and the constants a_i , b_i and c_i may be found in [15].

2. Strong Stability Preserving Runge-Kutta

A third-order three-stage strong-stability-preserving Runge-Kutta (SSPRK3), also known as total variation diminishing Runge-Kutta (TVD-RK), is also considered. Although not strictly needed in this work, however these time marching schemes are very useful in problems with shocks and discontinuities in general [15]. A reason for its usage here is the lesser stage-evaluation requirements. This may be given by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{p}_i &= (1 - \alpha_i)\mathbf{p}_{i-1} + \alpha_i\mathbf{p}_0 + \beta_i\delta t \cdot \mathbf{Res}\left(t^n + \gamma_i\delta t, \mathbf{p}_{i-1}\right), & (i = 1, \dots, 3), \\ \mathbf{W}^{n+1} &= \mathbf{p}_3, \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

with $\mathbf{p}_0 = \mathbf{W}^n$ and the coefficients are $\alpha = \{1, 3/4, 1/3\}$, $\beta = \{1, 1/4, 2/3\}$ and $\gamma = \{0, 1, 1/2\}$.

VI. Results

In this section, studies are carried out using two distinct solvers. In Section VI.A, a nodal-based dG two-dimensional Cartesian-coordinate solver, using quadrilateral-type elements, based on a conservative formulation is utilized. In Section VI.B, a modal-based dG three-dimensional curvilinear-coordinate solver that uses hexahedral-type elements is employed, utilizing an entropy formulation. Concerning time marching schemes, the 2D nodal solver uses a LSRK4 Section V.B.1, while the 3D modal solver uses a SSPRK3 Section V.B.2.

A. Two-dimensional Nodal Solver

In the context of the 2D nodal solver, two typical benchmark problems are considered: the isentropic vortex convection in Section VI.A.1 and the Kelvin-Helmholtz instability in Section VI.A.2. In each, a CBC and a PML simulation are carried out and compared. In all PML simulations, the terminating boundaries of the fictitious region are prescribed as CBC boundaries. The numerical flux used is that of Roe's [26].

1. Isentropic Vortex

One of the most common benchmarks considered for assessing NRBCs is the isentropic vortex problem. In essence, this canonical case is formed by superimposing a vortex on a uniform mean flow. The flow is along the x -direction in a domain $\Omega = [-1, 1] \times [-1, 1]$. The initial condition prescribed at $t_0 = 0$ is

$$\mathbf{U}(\mathbf{x}, t_0) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ U_0 \\ V_0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \rho' \\ -u' \sin \theta \\ u' \cos \theta \\ p' \end{pmatrix},$$

where the uniform flow is described by $V_0 = 0$ and $U_0 = M\gamma^{1/2}$, where M is the Mach number. The flow direction is aligned in the x -direction with $\theta = 0$. The disturbances are given by the relations

$$u' = -M\gamma^{1/2} \left(\varepsilon(y - y_0)e^{\frac{f}{4\pi r_0}} \right), \quad v' = M\gamma^{1/2} \left(\varepsilon(x - x_0)e^{\frac{f}{4\pi r_0}} \right), \quad \rho = \left[1 - \bar{\gamma}\varepsilon^2 M^2 e^{\frac{f}{8\pi^2}} \right]^{\frac{1}{\bar{\gamma}}}, \quad p = \rho^\gamma,$$

where the coefficients used are $\varepsilon = 1$, $f = 1 - r^2/r_0^2$ with $r = \sqrt{(x - x_0)^2 + (y - y_0)^2}$ being the radial distance, $(x_0, y_0) = (0, 0)$ as the vortex origin, and r_0 is the radial strength of the vortex. Two cases are considered: case A, which uses $M = 0.5$ and $r_0 = 0.1$, and case B, which uses $M = 0.8$ and $r_0 = 0.2$.

The grid used in the physical region is composed of 12×12 uniform elements, each described by a 6th-order polynomial using LGL nodes, resulting in 84×84 DOFs. Total simulation time is $t = 3$. Non-reflecting boundary conditions are imposed on all four sides. The left-most boundary is an inlet while the remaining three are outlets.

In the case of a CBC simulation, $\eta_\phi = 1$ and $\eta_2 = \eta_3 = \beta = 0$ are selected for an inlet, while $\sigma = 0.25$ and $\beta = M$ for an outlet. In all boundaries, the length-scale used is $l_x = l_y = 2$.

In the case of a PML simulation, a single layer of additional elements is wrapped about the physical domain in the y -direction, while a double layer of elements is used in the x -direction, each using a 3rd-order polynomial on LGL nodes as well.

Fig. 1 Case A; Density distribution and streamwise velocity contour plots taken at time $t = 0, 1, 1.75, 3$, from left to right, respectively; top and bottom rows correspond to a CBC and PML simulation, respectively.

Fig. 2 Case B; Density distribution and streamwise velocity contour plots taken at time $t = 0, 0.75, 1.25, 3$, from left to right, respectively; top and bottom rows correspond to a CBC and PML simulation, respectively.

Despite the inherent discontinuous nature of the scheme, whereby a constant coefficient may be used, yet the damping function selected is taken to be spatially-dependent and of the form

$$\sigma_x(x) = \sigma_m \left| \frac{x - x^{IT}}{D_x} \right|^\alpha, \quad \sigma_y(y) = \sigma_m \left| \frac{y - y^{IT}}{D_y} \right|^\alpha, \quad (35)$$

Fig. 3 L_2 -norm of the difference between the approximate and analytic solution in time, taken on the energy and x -momentum variables for case A (left) and case B (right).

where the superscript $(\cdot)^{IT}$ refers to the location of the interface between the PML and physical region, D_i is the respective PML thickness along the i th-direction, while α and σ_m are tuning coefficients for the damping functions.

In this example, the parameters used are $\alpha = 1$, $\sigma_m = 20$ and $D_x = h_x$ and $D_y = 2h_y$, with h_i denoting an element's length in the i th-direction. Terminating boundaries are still needed at the external boundaries in the PML region. Accordingly, a CBC is prescribed on all four boundaries using the same tuning parameters described above. Concerning the pseudo-mean flow at the fictitious layers, these were prescribed with the same initial condition.

In Figure 1, two identical simulations are showcased at four different time frames. These correspond to case A ($M = 0.5$ and $r_0 = 0.1$). From left to right, each of the columns correspond to snapshots taken at time $t = 0, 1, 1.75, 3$, respectively. The top row is that of a CBC simulation while the bottom row uses a PML simulation. Each panel depicts the density plot while the contours represent the streamwise velocity. Both simulations yield identical results and manage to preserve the correct speed of the vortex while exiting the domain. Reflections are evident in both simulations, albeit at negligible threshold.

In Figure 2, another set of two identical simulations are showcased. These are taken from case B ($M = 0.8$ and $r_0 = 0.2$) and at snapshots in time: $t = 0, 0.75, 1.25, 3$, from left to right, respectively. Due to the larger vortex, it is evident how, relative to case A, the numerical reflections are; albeit, at a marginal level still.

Figure 3 illustrates the L_2 -norm taken between the approximate solution and its analytical counterpart. The left and right panels correspond to case A and case B, respectively. The red and blue curves correspond to the x -momentum and total energy variables, respectively; triangle and square markers belong to an NSCBC and PML NRBC used, respectively. In both panels, it is evident how the accuracy of the solver degrades in time when the vortex approaches the NRBC and spurious reflections due to the open boundaries contaminate the solution.

2. Shear Flow

Another interesting benchmark problem with more complicated flow behavior is that of vortex shedding in a shear flow [18]. In this case, a time-dependent source term is introduced that will induce a Kelvin-Helmholtz instability which in turn will generate vortices. The total domain size is $\Omega = [-1, 9] \times [-1, 1]$.

The initial condition prescribed at $t_0 = 0$, in terms of primitive variables is

$$\bar{U}(y, t_0) = \frac{1}{2} \left[(U_1 + U_2) + (U_1 - U_2) \tanh \left(\frac{2y}{\delta} \right) \right],$$

with $\delta = 0.4$ and the density as

$$\rho(y, t_0) = \frac{1}{T(y)},$$

where the average temperature is given via the Crocco relation

$$\bar{T}(y, t_0) = T_1 \frac{\bar{U} - U_2}{U_1 - U_2} + T_2 \frac{U_1 - \bar{U}}{U_1 - U_2} + \frac{\bar{y}}{2} (U_1 - \bar{U})(\bar{U} - U_2),$$

with $U_1 = 0.8$, $U_2 = 0.2$, $T_1 = 1$ and $T_2 = 0.8$.

The source term responsible for the instability is added to the energy equation. It is of a Gaussian form with a sinusoidal time dependency and is expressed by

$$s(\mathbf{x}, t) = A_0 \sin(\omega t) e^{-\ln 2 \frac{r^2}{r_0^2}},$$

where $A_0 = 5$, $\omega = \pi/2$, $r_0 = 0.03$ and $r = \sqrt{(x - x_0)^2 + (y - y_0)^2}$ with the Gaussian origin at $(x_0, y_0) = (-0.5, 0)$.

The grid in the physical domain is identical in both simulations and is made of 28×16 elements, each described with a 4th-order polynomial using equidistant nodes, resulting in 140×80 DOFs. Total simulation time is $t = 35$. Non-reflecting boundary conditions are imposed on all four sides. The left-most side is prescribed as an inlet, in accordance with the initial conditions, while the remaining three are outlets.

Fig. 4 Density distribution and pressure contours plots taken at $t = 20$ (a) and $t = 35$ (b); in each panel, top and bottom figures correspond to a CBC and a PML simulation, respectively.

In the case of a CBC simulation, $\beta = 0.5$, $\eta_\phi = 1$, $\eta_2 = \eta_3 = 0$ are selected for an inlet, while $\sigma = 0.25$, $\beta = 0.5$ for an outlet along the x -direction and $\sigma = 0.25$, $\beta = 0.9$ for an outlet along the y -direction. In all boundaries, $l_x = 10$ and $l_y = 2$.

In the case of a PML simulation, two layers of additional elements is wrapped about the physical domain, each using a 3rd-order polynomial. The dispersion-relation correction constant is estimated as $\beta \approx U_0/(1 - U_0^2)$. The damping function, as given in Eq. (35), uses $\alpha = 2$, $\sigma_m = 20$ and $D_x = 5h_x$ and $D_y = 2h_y$. The number of element layers in each of the fictitious layers are 2 and 1 in the x - and y -layers, respectively, each described by a 3-order polynomial. Terminating boundaries are still needed at the external boundaries in the PML region. Accordingly, a CBC treatment is specified there, utilizing the same parameters as above.

In Fig. 4, two snapshots at different time intervals are taken; Fig. 4a is taken at $t = 20$ while Fig. 4b is at $t = 35$. In each panel, the top figure refers to the CBC simulation and the bottom one to that of a PML. Each of the figures display the pressure contours superimposed on the density plots, while retaining the same scale with respect to their counterpart panel. Both simulations manage to capture the correct vortical structures towards the exit, although in the case of the CBC, the vortices are not convected at the correct speed. This is evident from the pressure contours in the bottom panels, as compared to their top counterparts. This slight shift is also confirmed when compared against a reference solution taken in a larger domain $\Omega^{ref} = [-1.5, 15]$, (not shown).

B. Three-dimensional Modal Solver

In this section, a modal 3D solver is used and applied on two test cases: a pressure pulse in a quiescent flow Section VI.B.1 and a more challenging case of a flow past a wall-mounted hump Section VI.B.2. In each of the problems, two NRBCs are considered: an extrapolation method based on the Riemann invariants and a NSCBC. In all this section, the dynamic viscosity was set constant, $\mu = 1.716 \cdot 10^{-5} [N \cdot s \cdot m^{-2}]$. Additionally, the numerical flux used for the convective part is that of Ismail-Roe [27].

1. Pressure Pulse

Another classic problem for testing non-reflective boundaries is via a pressure pulse superimposed on a quiescent flow ($M = 0$). In [16], this was used in order to asses the performance of edges and corners for a NSCBC. In this work however, no special treatment for corners or edges were considered. The domain considered is a cube of $\Omega = [0, L]^3$ while the pressure pulse specified is spherical and given by

$$p(r) = p_\infty \left(1 + \delta \cdot e^{-\frac{r^2}{2R_p^2}} \right), \quad (36)$$

where the radial distance from the center of the pulse is $r = \sqrt{(x - x_0)^2 + (y - y_0)^2 + (z - z_0)^2}$, $R_p = 0.04$, $\delta = 0.08$, and the pulse center (x_0, y_0, z_0) was taken in the middle of the domain at $(0.5, 0.5, 0.5)$, while the domain size is defined by $L = 1 [m]$. The pressure was initialized to $p_\infty = 94547.0585 [Pa]$, $T_\infty = 298.93 [k]$ and $u_\infty = v_\infty = w_\infty = 0$.

The grid used is comprised of $12 \times 12 \times 12$ elements, each described by a 5th-order polynomial, based on LGL nodes, resulting in $72 \times 72 \times 72$ DOFs. This was used in both Riemann and NSCBC simulations.

In the case of a NSCBC treatment, $\sigma = 0.25$, the transverse term parameters were set to $\beta_t = 0.5$ and $\beta_l = 1$ in Equation (23), while the target pressure to p_∞ . The solution was marched in time until the pulse traveled well-past the domain.

The domain's cube geometry as well as the pressure wave evolving in time is displayed in Figure 5. The top row corresponds to a Riemann boundary treatment, while the bottom row denotes that of an NSCBC. Each column is taken at the same time, from left to right, $t = 1 \cdot 10^{-4}$, $t = 1.4 \cdot 10^{-4}$, $t = 1.8 \cdot 10^{-4}$, $t = 2.2 \cdot 10^{-4}$, and $t = 2.8 \cdot 10^{-4} [s]$, respectively. In both cases, the same color-scale has been used. Indeed it is evident how comparatively reflective the Riemann-based extrapolation method is as opposed to a NSCBC one. The effect of such reflections can be seen in the L_2 -norm taken on the difference between each of the two simulations and a corresponding reference solution. Refer to Figure 6. The reference solution was obtained by taking a domain twice as long per dimension $L^{ref} = 2L$ described by twice the number of elements per dimension $24 \times 24 \times 24$ with the same polynomial order. Hence the same element resolution is retained, while a NSCBC treatment was imposed on all boundaries. Although this is a benchmark problem, nevertheless one does realize the implications on the accuracy of the solver when these numerical reflections bounce back into the domain.

Fig. 5 Pressure taken at different snapshots in time as it evolves, from left to right; top and bottom rows correspond to a Riemann and a NSCBC treatment, respectively.

As mentioned previously, no special treatment of edges and corners has been introduced. This was motivated by the observation that in a dG formulation, the boundary is applied directly on the integration points, which do not live on edges or corners. Moreover, the NSCBC implementation is directly applied on the ghost/external-state nodes via a polynomial correction approach described in Equation (24) through a least-squares method.

Fig. 6 L_2 -norm of the difference between approximate solutions and a reference solution; Riemann (red) and NSCBC (blue).

2. NASA Hump Case

The final example considered is that of a flow past a hump. This problem is the third case in [28–31]. The reference experimental data is based on [30, 31].

The computational domain used is of the size $L_x \times L_y \times L_z$ with $L_x \approx 10.4c$, $L_y \approx 0.91c$ and $L_z = 0.4c$, where $c = 0.42$ [mm] is the chord (hump) length. The total number of elements used in the discretization were $50 \times 13 \times 10$, each described by 5th-order polynomials utilizing LGL nodes. Refer to Figure 7, for illustration. In terms of DOFs, this is equivalent to $300 \times 78 \times 60$, or 1 404 000 overall.

The flow is defined by a target $Re = 936\,000$, based on a freestream $M = 0.1$. In the streamwise (x -)direction, from the left, total conditions are prescribed at the inlet with $p_t = 95247.737858$ [Pa] and $T_t = 298.93$ [k], with velocity aligned in the streamwise x -direction, while a pressure outlet is prescribed downstream with $p = 94547.0585$ [Pa]. Periodic boundary conditions are specified in the spanwise (z -)direction. In the wall-normal (y -)direction, at the upper boundary an inviscid wall is prescribed, while at the bottom boundary, a zero-heat flux wall is used along with a wall-modeling approach based on the logarithmic wall model [32].

Fig. 7 Grid near the hump; dark black lines correspond to entire elements.

Four simulations were carried out using the same configurations and on the same grid, partially illustrated in Figure 7. The first two are referred to as *case A* (Riemann) and *case B* (NSCBC), implying the inlet and outlets are treated via a Riemann-based extrapolation and an NSCBC approach, respectively. The second two utilize a wall-adapting local eddy-viscosity (WALE) [33] subgrid-scale modeling method and are referred to as *case Aw* (Riemann with WALE model) and *case Bw* (NSCBC with WALE model). In the case of the NSCBC methods, no transverse terms were included by setting $\beta = 0$ in both inlets and outlets. As for the inlet, total conditions were prescribed and then used in order to update the target state. This however, proved not very stable when running the simulations for an extended period of time. A more suitable and consistent approach would be to consider the framework introduced in [34].

In all four simulations, a transient period of $\Delta t^{tr} \approx 1.8c/U_0$ was discarded before starting the averaging in time. The total simulation time was $\Delta t^{tot} \approx 10.8c/U_0$, of which 9 out of 10.8 ‘flow-through’ times were reserved for statistical data sampling, before finally collapsing the data in the homogeneous (spanwise) direction. A flow-through time is defined based on the bulk velocity U_0 in the streamwise direction and the chord length c .

Fig. 8 Coefficient of pressure at the wall; case A (green), case B (purple), case Aw (red), case Bw (blue) and reference experimental data (black).

In Figure 8, the wall-pressure coefficient is portrayed for all four simulations along with their reference experimental data. The pressure coefficient is defined as

$$C_p = \frac{p - p_0}{\frac{1}{2}\rho_0 U_0^2},$$

where all $(\cdot)_0$ quantities are based on the freestream values taken at $x/c \approx -2.14$, in accordance with the experimental set-up.

All simulations give results that differ significantly from the experimental results. However, the presence of an explicit turbulence model does seem to tend towards the right trend. This is further confirmed in Figure 9, where the averaged flow properties are plot at $x/c = 1$. From left to right, these are the (normalized with the streamwise bulk velocity) averaged quantities: wall-normal velocity, and Re-stresses uu , uv and vv , respectively. Colors indicate case A

Fig. 9 Averaged normalized flow properties of all four simulations and reference experimental data taken at $x/c = 1$; left to right, wall-normal velocity, Re-stresses in the uu , uv and vv direction, respectively.

(green), case B (purple), case Aw (red), case Bw (blue), and the experimental data (black). Indeed, the presence of an active turbulence model does play a role in capturing some of the turbulent flow data from experiments. These findings imply that the grid used is still relatively too coarse to properly capture the turbulent flow characteristics accurately, as well as the reattachment location.

Fig. 10 Instantaneous pressure visualized at $t \approx 1.8c/U_0$ (a) and $t \approx 5.4c/U_0$ (b); in each panel, top and bottom figures correspond to a case Aw and case Bw, respectively.

Nonetheless, the primary aim of this set-up is to compare and contrast the efficacy of the non-reflective boundaries included thus far. Accordingly, one immediately observes the difference in the instantaneous pressure field. For instance, in Figure 10, the instantaneous pressure is presented at two different times: $t \approx 1.8c/U_0$ in Figure 10a and $t \approx 5.4c/U_0$ in Figure 10b. In each of the figures, the top and bottom panels corresponds to case Aw and case Bw, respectively. The extent of the numerical contamination, due to pressure waves bouncing partially back into the domain, is very clear. This is mildly present in the NSCBC approach, as opposed to the exaggerated Riemann-based extrapolation technique, despite the large domain and increasingly coarse element sizes as they approach the specified NRBCs. At the final time of the simulation, $t \approx 10.8c/U_0$, the level of numerical contamination in the solution is still evident around the hump, as depicted in Figure 11. Besides, even in Figures 8 and 9, despite the grid being coarse and the boundaries are relatively far away from the hump, with grid elements geometrically growing coarser in their vicinity, yet differences still appear when comparing an extrapolation method vs a NSCBC treatment.

Fig. 11 Instantaneous Mach number near the bottom wall with instantaneous pressure slice and its contour in a wall-normal plane taken at $t \approx 10.8c/U_0$; case Aw (a) and case Bw (b).

VII. Conclusion and Future Work

In an effort to develop different non-reflective boundary conditions in the context of the discontinuous Galerkin framework, multiple simulations were carried out. Both, a two-dimensional solver utilizing a nodal approach and a three-dimensional solver using a modal approach were considered. High-order polynomials were used and two distinct (explicit) time marching schemes were taken into account, a LSRK4 and a SSPRK3. In the nodal form, a conservative formulation was used, while an entropy one was chosen for the modal form. The NRBCs employed are that of a PML and a NSCBC, while an extrapolation method based on Riemann invariants was also tested. The NSCBC was enforced via a polynomial-correction approach.

In the two-dimensional nodal solver, results were carried out on two traditional benchmark cases: the isentropic vortex and the Kelvin-Helmholtz instability via shear flow. In both cases, an NSCBC and a PML with NSCBC as terminating boundaries were used. Both results proved adequate in mitigating most numerical reflections.

In the three-dimensional modal solver, problems considered were a spherical pressure disturbance and a flow past a hump. In both cases, a NSCBC and an extrapolation method were used. The NSCBC demonstrated much better results, while the extrapolation technique showed poor outcomes, despite placing the NRBCs far from the region of interest and using very coarse elements there.

This preliminary investigation is an ongoing effort in order to apply different NRBCs in the context of the dG framework. Upcoming progress will include the PML in generalized three-dimensions with viscous treatment, along with the NSCBC as terminating boundary conditions. Moreover, edge and corner nodes treatment in the context of the NSCBC will be included in order to mitigate any instabilities that might arise from adjacent boundary conditions specified.

Eventually, this work will be extended towards more generalized, two- and three-dimensional problems, using unstructured grids, in the context of the high-order dG solver in the open-source CFD code, **SU2***.

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*<https://su2code.github.io/>

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